

Governing Major Infrastructure Projects in Laos: The Context of Front-End

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Abstract—For pursuing development goal, the governance of major infrastructure projects in Laos should be investigated from the front-end phase, it's the first step to examine essential requirements and highlight both positive and negatively affect to the whole project. This research this research had explored the decision-making process, governance framework, assessment method, roles and responsibility of public infrastructure projects as the *front-end governance context in Laos*. Data from public documents and literature can be drawn a whole picture of front-end governance context, and case studies can provide us with a better understanding of real context (phenomenon). The synthesizing analysis can be explored the *parties, roles and the staged-gated process* of front-end decision for a better understanding of decision-making in major infrastructure projects

Keywords—Project governance, major infrastructure projects, front-end phase, Laos

I. INTRODUCTION

For pursuing development goal and poverty reduction, Government of Lao (GoL) has proposed “*Land-lock to Land-link*” as the most important strategy that links Laos with neighboring countries toward transportation network from regional to international integration, the strategy had focused on sustainable development goals and connectivity¹. Under development programs², the GoL had launched many major infrastructure projects for rural infrastructure as a necessary prerequisite for poverty reduction and sustainable growth³. However, the challenges on major infrastructure projects in developing countries are very high [1]. For solving the problems, we should first go back to the front-end phase, and it's the first step to examine essential requirements that would help decision makers to weigh up competing interests to the right decision. For securing projects success or failure and also the crucial decision-making in the front-end phase can provide both positive and negatively affect the project outcome [2]–[5].

This research aims to explore the decision-making process, governance framework, assessment method, roles and responsibility of public organization in the early project's

¹ Master Plan on ASEAN Connectivity, 2025 (MPAC 2025)

² 8th Five-Year National Socio-Economic Development Plan (2016-2020): LAO PDR, Ministry of Planning and Investment

³ ADB. 2006. *Country Partnership Strategy: Lao People's Democratic Republic, 2007–2011*

studies that known as *front-end governance*. The research conducts with the qualitative approach for overarching front-end governance of public investment project by following [2], [6]. Firstly, the synthesizing analysis can explore the decision-making process in the front-end phase with its governance framework, mechanism, and responsible organization. Then, the investigation of four case studies of major infrastructure projects in Laos can provide us the better understanding of real context (phenomenon) in the front-end phase to outline the parties and roles and the staged-gated process of front-end decision. Finally, to make this research more interesting, the result can be discussed with the principles of front-end governance in other countries to find “what front-end need” for a better understanding of public decision and highlights the potential improvement of infrastructure development.

II. FRONT-END GOVERNANCE

The *front-end* has become the first step to examine essential requirements that would help decision makers, the decision-making in projects are made in the front-end phase, and it can provide both positive, and negative affected. Thus, study in this phase is significant to examine essential requirements that would help decision makers to weigh up competing interests to a right decision and can be securing for projects long-term success and project failure [4], [5], thus any failures in this phase will identify the critical issues and difficulties of the whole projects. Research on front-end governance can be understood on the governance framework to provides the management structures, processes, roles and responsibilities, communication and controlling process to ensure the selection of the right project concepts [7]–[12].

Figure 1. Project planning process

Source: Lao PDR, Ministry of Planning and Investment, MPIPM

Recently, front-end governance of major public investment project in many countries had examined with the stage-gate model, as well as the involved parties and roles in the front-end decision-making process [2], [6]. Meanwhile, many studies examined front-end governance process under the institutional context [7], [13]–[17]. In the book of “*The Strategic Management of Large Engineering Projects: Shaping Institutions, Risk, and Governance*” [18] mentioned to the models of organizing and institution contexts through essential impacts on infrastructure project performance. An active and influential organization is the foundation for project success. Many infrastructure practices around the world indicate the government is one of the principal actors, in UK and Norway, government organizations set several approval procedures for public projects in the front-end [2], [11]. In China, the government also promotes infrastructure projects by executing organizational strength, forcing authorities to temporarily integrate the processes for the benefit of the project, resource selection decisions, and leadership accountability.

III. GOVERNANCE OF MAJOR INFRASTRUCTURE PROJECTS

Major infrastructure projects have been considering at the national level [19] that delivery through the public investments projects, Direct provision, Traditional public procurement, State-owned enterprises, Public-Private Partnerships (PPP) and Concessions and Privatization with the regulation [20]–[22] with long-term goals. The governance of major public projects always deals with the political processes [23] for achieving the development goals or the right public project [12], [24]. Moreover, the governance of infrastructure deal with the processes, tools, and norms of interaction, decision-making, and monitoring used by governmental organizations and their counterparts for making infrastructure services available to the public and the private sector.

However, the governance of infrastructure projects should provide a structured mechanism to identify and address risks [25] as infrastructure projects occur. Nowadays many countries delivery major infrastructure projects through PPPs, it can be fulfilling the infrastructure development to achieve their goals as well as loans. Instead of direct public procurement, the projects are often delivered through the involvement of private-sector firms in the financing, design, delivery, and operation of the infrastructure [26]. PPPs model can achieve proper risk allocation in tollway projects that are developed under the PPP procurement system which would enhance the project's performance [27] and contractual governance for risk allocation that imply early partner involvement, risk and benefit sharing and highly collaborative project delivery [28] and can be improving project performance [29], [30].

IV. THE CHARACTERISTICS OF FRONT-END GOVERNANCE IN LAOS

A. Governance framework and decision-making process

In Laos, the governance of public investment project has following the “*Public Investment Law*,” it should be in the line of the National Socio-Economic Development Plans (NSEDPs) and sector strategies in the relevant areas as well as relevance to the achievement of development plan targets. The front-end process of public investment project in Laos called “Project Planning” that started from project identification until the approval stage by National Assembly, illustrated in “Fig.1”.

- Project identification ideally is conducted through studies during the formulation stages for development plans and incorporated in the medium-term public investment plan. It focuses on finding the basic idea and needs of a project that fit the Socio-Economic Development Plans (SEDPs) and sector strategies in the relevant areas. It's usually conducted by the potential project owner and its sector organization, and close collaboration officials that the potential project will be located.
- Feasibility studies are conducted to examine whether a planned public investment construction project is feasible in economic, social and environmental aspects. As well as its relevance to the achievement of development plan targets, which provides the basic outline and feasibility of the new potential public investment project in the subject that a project has an absolute requirement for technical survey and design for construction.
- Project Proposal is the official document of the public investment project which must be submitted every time a new project is requested including *Feasibility Studies, Designing, Environmental and Social Assessment*. Its objective is to provide information on the contents of the new project and show that the request is appropriately planned and ready for implementation
- Assessment for a feasibility study (F/S) will then assess whether the F/S can be implemented and allocated with the development budget that depends on the type of the project, and organization of project owner is attached.
- Project Formulation is the first designing step of the project framework. Based on social needs and priorities of development, the public investment project is formulated by specifying the *Project Purpose* and the *Overall Goal*.
- Proposal for Construction is detailed project information and necessary certification that will be assessed whether the public investment project can be implemented or be allocated within the development budget.

The approval process of the project planning phase is a stage where public investment projects are identified, formulated and designed, and it is also a step where necessary environmental, disaster prevention, climate risk, and social assessments are made. In the stage of project planning, potential public investment projects are identified by searching needs of beneficiaries and finding the means to achieve their objectives. After the public investment project in need is planned the sector department shall appoint the potential project owner to formulate the project in detail, including the specific analysis of its relevance and effectiveness. It will obtain an assessment from Government Meeting and the National Assembly for final approval.

B. Front-end assessment

In 2014, the Ministry of Planning and Investment of Laos (MPI) had proposed the evaluation method for public investment projects classified into two categories as *assessment and evaluation*. The assessment method is used for examining the early phase project on whether it is necessary to start or continue the implementation. For achieving the development goal, the public investment projects in Laos use the Simplified Project Assessment Sheet (SPAS) for front-end and implementation phase and Simplified Project Evaluation Sheet (SPES) for terminal and ex-post evaluation.

Front-end assessment method or *simplified project assessment sheet (SPAS)* is **the** first steps to examine the public investment project before it is approved, it also examines whether it is worthwhile to allocate the budget. Its focus on the performance of a public investment project in five evaluation criteria that based on the Development Assistance Committee (DAC) evaluation standard of (OECD)⁴, illustrated in "Table I." Likewise, the most critical points to check including 1). The project must be relevant to development plans, 2). The project must have economic relevance as the results of NPV, B/C or IRR. 3). Feasibility is clear and logical relations among inputs and activities, outputs and the project purpose.

TABLE I. THE FIVE EVALUATION CRITERIA

CRITERIA	DEFINITION
Relevance	1). <i>The consistency of the project purpose and overall goal with development and policy targets, 2). Appropriateness of the project purpose in line with the needs of beneficiaries, region, and economy, etc.</i>
Effectiveness	<i>Achievement of project purpose or expectations of its achievement.</i>
Efficiency	1). <i>Appropriateness of project inputs and its utilization, including costs planned, used and disbursed, 2). Actions for social and environmental approaches.</i>
Impact	<i>Any indirect effect caused by the project, negative impacts on the society and environment is stressed.</i>
Sustainability	<i>Sustainability of the project outputs and its direct effect after completion.</i>

Source: Lao PDR, Ministry of Planning and Investment, NSEDP

⁴ DAC, Principles for Evaluation of Development Assistance (1991)

V. CASE STUDIES

A. Case1&case2: Major urban development project1 and project2 (GMS1&GMS2)

Greater Mekong Subregion1 (GMS1) project was started June 2012, including three corridor towns: Kaysone Phomvihane, Phine, and Dansavanh district. Although, the second project represented *Greater Mekong Subregion2 (GMS2)*, had started from July 2015 including two towns, Houayxay, and Luang Namtha district. Both of GMS1&GMS2 serve as dynamic centers of investment and economic growth for a local community in the hinterlands of the corridor towns for the development of urban infrastructure and essential support services. The front-end governance of *GMS1&GMS2* takes place by the Government of Lao and the Asian Development Bank (ADB) considerable emphasis of project's concept and vision on developing priority transport corridors to forge the physical connectivity among the Greater Mekong Sub-region (GMS) projects in Laos.

In the project's concept and vision is conducted by government and funding agency such as ADB and Department of housing and urban planning (DHU) have full responsibility for this phase. While, the project steering committee (PSC) will be created to provide overall policy guidance and oversee of pre-project study under the objectives and scope of the Project. In the feasibility studies phase had launched by the exclusive agency that had created the project coordination unit (PCU) to have a full response of project study. Finally, the decision and approval phase had direct response by parent level that had reported the final assessment from Ministry of Planning and Investment (MPI) for assessment and checklist in the annual development plan request flow follows for each of the public development projects, and further on submitted to the National Assembly for final approval, illustrated in "Fig.2".

B. Case3&case4: Major transportation development projects (NR13&NR2)

The National Road 13 North (NR13) considering as the "Asian Highway" to fulfilled the new economic cooperation circle among "Golden Four Corner Belt" in three countries including China, Laos, and Thailand. Due to the drainage system of the whole road is not perfect and poor indivisibility. Therefore, the project had been rehabilitated and improved from May 2015. Likewise, *The National Road No.2 (NR2)* located in the northwest of Laos, it aims to link Thailand and Vietnam to Northern Laos, also considered a part of "Asian Highway Network." Although, the current road is in low standards and lack of maintenance. Thus the government had been developed from June 2013. The two NR13&NR2 have been a considering as the regional projects, upcoming country program, infrastructure and rural development program for improving connectivity with neighboring countries which makes the establishment of an accountable, effective, transparent, and responsive public administration to strengthen service delivery a key development objective that intent to transition from a "land-locked" to a "land-linked" country.

In the concept and vision stage had launched by the government and development partner that ADB focus on the development of regional roads connectivity in Asian countries. Similar with GMS, the project steering committee had created from Ministry of Public work and Transport (MPWT), Ministry of Finance (MOF), Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment (MONRE), Ministry of Planning and Investment (MPI) and other related organizations for responsible oversees program development and provides overall guidance. The feasibility study stage also responded from the exclusive agency like the Department of Road (DOR) under MPWT had responsibility for the development plans consistently to support the expansion of the road network.

Figure 2. Front-end process of GMS1&GMS2

Figure 3. Front-end process of NR13&NR

In this state, A project coordination unit (PCU) within MPWT and DOR will have overall coordination responsibility and work closely with the provincial DPWTs for all over the work of feasibility study. While, Regional Advisory Committee (RAC) and international consultant knew as consultation to supporting potential data with oversight, coordination and supporting all the study process for setting standards, allocating resources, monitoring, providing technical support including training to provincial authorities, overseeing quality assurance systems. Finally, in the decision and approval phase had a deal by National Assembly's meeting which the overall flow of administrative works follows what the Ministry of Planning and Investment (MPI) instruct of the public investment projects, the projects will be prioritized and checked whether they are listed for the annual budget request. While, the provincial assemblies of three-province have the mandate to review, approve, and overseer of the provincial socio-economic development plan as the legislative mechanism at the sub-national level. Finally, overall results had submitted to the Government Meeting and confirmed by the National Assembly for final approval, illustrated in "Fig.3".

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This section discussed the context of front-end governance in Laos with the principle from other countries, and it might highlight some points to show us the differences and characteristics of those governance contexts. In the discussion, we had concluded the principle of front-end governance in Laos from the public document as the guideline of public projects, roles, and responsibility of the organization, public investment law and case studies which discussed on following key points.

- According to the front-end governance of six OECD countries [6], the front-end context of major infrastructure projects in Laos had summarized as the *parties and roles*, illustrated in "Fig.4". It can be highlighting the whole context of a public project in Laos, especially in the front-end decision phase. It is shown that the project appraisals phase is conducted at the ministries level to the coordinator and principle guideline to public investment project and requires quality assurers to examine the quality of public investment project. Then the decision phase is conducted with central government and parliament (National Assembly) for its approval and final decision.
- From the observation, the front-end assessment method in Laos has the focus to requirement of the government plan, and less on the other perspectives and the challenges is that some assessment requirements are not even used for front-end assessment, e.g., *effectiveness and efficiency*.
- Reviewing to internal context of major public projects between transport and urban development projects had some similarities and differences. It has similar on the

decision-making process, governance framework and role of the public organization. However, it has some different regarding the regional organization that transportation projects cover huge area than another one, e.g., there are three provincial assemblies and governments jointed to feasibility studies and decision phase. Therefore, the investigated of public organizations are varies.

- The stage-gate model of public investment project in Laos had investigated for further discussion. The model is classification into four phases 1). *Project identification*, 2). *Feasibility proposal*, 3). *Front-end assessment*, and 4). *Project approval*, illustrated in "Fig.5". There is a simple arrangement of front-end assessment in Laos that contains only one assessment method (SPAS) with two decision points (government and parliament decisions). While in OECD countries had applied the different method for project approval, e.g., QA1 for examining the choice of concept and QA2 examine the cost estimation and cost control, and there are five stages decision in Quebec and UK for front-end assessment.

Figure 4. Parties and roles of the major infrastructure project in Laos

Figure 5. The stage-gate model in the front-end phase

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Mackhaphonh and G. Jia, "Megaprojects in Developing Countries and their Challenges," *Int. J. Business, Econ. Manag. Work.*, vol. 4, no. 11, pp. 6–12, 2017.
- [2] G. H. Volden and K. Samset, "Governance of Major Public Investment Projects: Principles and Practices in Six Countries," *Proj. Manag. J.*, vol. 48, no. 3, pp. 90–108, 2017.
- [3] T. Christensen, "The Norwegian front-end governance regime of major public projects: A theoretically based analysis and evaluation," *Int. J. Manag. Proj. Bus.*, vol. 4, pp. 218–239, 2011.
- [4] R. Garland, *Project Governance: A Practical Guide to Effective Project Decision Making*. London, UK, 2009.
- [5] K. Samset and G. H. Volden, "Front-end definition of projects: Ten paradoxes and some reflections regarding project management and project governance," *Int. J. Proj. Manag.*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 297–313, 2016.
- [6] K. F. Samset and G. H. Volden, *Governance Schemes for Major Public Investment Projects: A comparative study of principles and practices in six countries*, no. 47, 2016.
- [7] P. W. G. Morris and J. Gherardi, "Managing the institutional context for projects," *Proj. Manag. J.*, vol. 42, no. 6, pp. 20–32, 2011.
- [8] B. Hobbs and M. Aubry, "An Empirically Grounded Search for a Typology of Project Management Offices," *Proj. Manag. J.*, vol. 39, pp. S69–S82, 2008.
- [9] E. S. Andersen, "Illuminating the role of the project owner," *Int. J. Manag. Proj. Bus.*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 67–85, 2012.
- [10] R. Müller, *Project governance*, vol. 12, no. 5, 2009.
- [11] O. J. Klakegg, T. Williams, and O. M. Magnussen, "Governance Frameworks for Public Project Development and Estimation," *Proj. Manag. J.*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 47–67, 2008.
- [12] A. Tadege Shiferaw and O. Jonny Klakegg, "Linking policies to projects: The key to identifying the right public investment projects," *Project Management Journal*, vol. 43, no. 4, pp. 14–26, 2012.
- [13] V. S. K. Delhi and A. Mahalingam, "Institutional issues related to project governance of infrastructure PPP projects in India," in *Construction Research Congress © ASCE 2012*, 2012, pp. 1481–1490.
- [14] M. Hobday, "The project-based organisation: an ideal form for managing complex products and systems?," *Res. Policy*, vol. 29, no. 7–8, pp. 871–893, 2000.
- [15] C. Besner and B. Hobbs, "Project Management Practice, Generic or Contextual: A Reality Check," *Proj. Manag. J.*, vol. 39, no. 1, pp. 16–33, 2008.
- [16] A. K. Y. Ng, A. E. Velasco-Acosta, and T. Wang, "Institutions and the governance of transport infrastructure projects: Some insight from the planning and construction of the CentrePort Canada Way," *Res. Transp. Bus. Manag.*, vol. 14, pp. 25–33, 2015.
- [17] R. A. W. Rhodes, "Understanding Governance: Ten Years On," *Organ. Stud.*, vol. 28, no. 8, pp. 1243–1264, 2007.
- [18] R. Miller and D. Lessard, *The Strategic Management of Large Engineering Projects (Book)*, vol. 33, no. 1, 2002.
- [19] O. J. Klakegg, "Pursuing relevance and sustainability: Improvement strategies for major public projects," *Int. J. Manag. Proj. Bus.*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 499–518, 2009.
- [20] OECD, "Regulation of Insurance Company and Pension Fund Investment OECD REPORT TO G20 FINANCE MINISTERS AND CENTRAL BANK GOVERNORS," *OECD Rep. 2015*, no. September, pp. 1–37, 2015.
- [21] O. Jonny Klakegg and T. Haavaldsen, "Governance of major public investment projects: in pursuit of relevance and sustainability," *Int. J. Manag. Proj. Bus.*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 157–167, 2011.
- [22] Z. A. Auzzir, R. P. Haigh, and D. Amaratunga, "Public-private Partnerships (PPP) in Disaster Management in Developing Countries: A Conceptual Framework," *Procedia Econ. Financ.*, vol. 18, pp. 807–814, 2014.
- [23] T. Williams, O. J. Klakegg, O. M. Magnussen, and H. Glasspool, "An investigation of governance frameworks for public projects in Norway and the UK," *Int. J. Proj. Manag.*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 40–50, 2010.
- [24] T. Cooke-Davies, "The 'real' success factors on projects," *Int. J. Proj. Manag.*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 185–190, 2002.
- [25] F. Guo, Y. Chang-Richards, S. Wilkinson, and T. C. Li, "Effects of project governance structures on the management of risks in major infrastructure projects: A comparative analysis," *Int. J. Proj. Manag.*, vol. 32, no. 5, pp. 815–826, 2014.
- [26] D. Walker and M. Jacobsson, "A rationale for alliancing within a public-private partnership," *Eng. Constr. Archit. Manag.*, vol. 21, no. 6, pp. 648–673, 2014.
- [27] M. P. Abednego and S. O. Ogunlana, "Good project governance for proper risk allocation in public-private partnerships in Indonesia," *Int. J. Proj. Manag.*, vol. 24, no. 7, pp. 622–634, 2006.
- [28] J. R. Turner and S. J. Simister, "Project contract management and a theory of organization," *Int. J. Proj. Manag.*, vol. 19, no. 8, pp. 457–464, 2001.
- [29] J. Halman and B. Braks, "Project alliancing in the offshore industry," *Int. J. Proj. Manag.*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 71–76, 1999.
- [30] M. Suprpto, H. L. M. Bakker, H. G. Mooi, and M. J. C. M. Hertogh, "How do contract types and incentives matter to project performance?," *Int. J. Proj. Manag.*, vol. 34, no. 6, pp. 1071–1087, 2016.

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